

FLUX LEADERSHIP: VOCATIONAL SCHOOL PRINCIPAL LEADERSHIP TO SUPPORT POST-COVID-19 LEARNING RECOVERY

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Abstract

Flux leadership introduces a generative framework for agile, responsive, and healing-centered leadership in times of crisis. This strategic step is called a leadership strategy, a policy taken by the school principal to respond to the current pandemic. This research aims to determine the extent to which school principals apply flux leadership and what the role of flux leadership is in the leadership of vocational school principals to support post-COVID-19 learning recovery. The research was carried out using a quantitative approach using survey methods. The research was conducted in June – August 2022. The research location was at a vocational school in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The population and sample in this research are school principals and/or deputy principals of vocational schools in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The data collection technique uses a questionnaire followed by quantitative descriptive analysis. research shows that the successful implementation of flux leadership can be achieved best by applying a radical growth mindset, distributed wisdom approach, leading from an inquiry stance, trauma-informed leadership, radical compassion and radical self-care, responsive and humanizing leadership, leader critical pedagogy, racial literacy, brave space leadership, emotional imagination, and inner-resource cultivation. Vocational school principals need to understand what factors influence leadership in organizations so they can adapt to the uncertainty following the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, managers can develop post-Covid-19 flux leadership skills to encourage effective school performance.

Keywords: Flux Leadership, Leadership, School Principals, Learning Recovery, Post-Covid-19

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia confirmed the first case of COVID-19 on March 2, 2020, when formal educational institutions implemented Learning from Home [1]. There are 646,200 schools in Indonesia ranging from PAUD to tertiary institutions, so 68.8 million students are studying at home, and 4.2 million teachers and lecturers are teaching from home (Darmawan, 2020), using the Learning Management System, video conferences, and social platforms. Media for learning from home (Gunawan et al., 2020). Online learning is a solution used during the Covid-19 pandemic (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020).

Several studies, including Widiyono (2020), concluded that online learning activities result in less effective learning. Many problems arise from the home learning policy, including the student learning process, assessments, and the opportunity to get a job after graduating from education (Aryansah & Sari, 2021).

The impacts that arise in online learning not only affect the student process and output but also influence the trust of graduate users in the quality of graduates. To ensure the quality of

education in education units, leaders who can develop and make policies that suit the school's needs are needed. The principal as a leader is an essential factor that significantly influences the quality of education in a school, or it could be said that achieving the quality of education in a school is primarily determined by the school principal's leadership. School principals, as leaders of educational institutions, must also be ready to face and adapt to challenges in any situation, including the COVID-19 pandemic that is currently occurring. School principals need to design strategic steps to improve the quality of education in the schools they lead during the pandemic and post-Covid-19.

The challenge in managing educational institutions today is the availability of quality human resources. If the school principals lack human relations, technical, and conceptual skills, the school practices will be ineffective (Supriadi et al., 2021). As a leader, the principal must have abilities in all management, motivation, policy-making, and socializing areas. The school principal is responsible for managing the educational institution he leads to create quality educational activities by mobilizing all school components to work together to achieve educational goals. As the control holder and policy maker, the school principal can formulate policies that suit the school's needs to improve the quality of school education by involving all components, including teachers, students, parents, and the community. The school principal's leadership must be able to mobilize all school components to work together to improve the quality of education. The school principal must also be able to establish good communication and socialization with the community in order to create a quality school that meets the needs of the wider community, so it can be concluded that the leadership of a school principal who can carry out his role will lead to the achievement of quality education, especially after the Covid-19 pandemic.

In times of rapid change, such as a global pandemic, school principals as educational leaders need tools and frameworks that can adapt to changes that develop in real-time. Flux leadership is a framework that allows collaborative inquiry to occur in real time to answer complex questions and sudden changes. Flux leadership introduces a generative framework for agile, responsive, and healing-centered leadership in times of crisis.

This strategic step is called a leadership strategy, a policy taken by the school principal to respond to the current pandemic. Based on this phenomenon, discussing the school principal's leadership strategy with flux leadership in supporting learning recovery after the COVID-19 pandemic is interesting.

The problem of this research is "How is the leadership of school principals in supporting post-Covid-19 learning recovery? To what extent do school principals adopt flux leadership as an alternative strategy to support post-COVID-19 learning recovery?."

LITERATURE REVIEW

The implementation of Vocational High Schools (SMK) aims to prepare students to have skills as productive workers and be able to create jobs through entrepreneurship. Vocational education in Indonesia tends to apply a human resources planning approach, emphasizing the

suitability of vocational school graduates with workforce needs in the industrial world (Reddy, 2005). Therefore, vocational school management is more oriented towards learning designed to prepare graduates to enter the world of work. In order to achieve educational goals in vocational schools, school principals must have adequate managerial skills to manage and overcome problems in vocational schools. School principals must be able to answer the challenges of problems in Vocational Schools related to whether Vocational School graduates have been maximally absorbed in industrial work. Do vocational school graduates have a guarantee of a job position following their field of expertise? Have the curriculum, teacher resources, and infrastructure followed and adapted to dynamic industrial developments?

There are facts from various research results that show that vocational school education management still needs to be more optimal. The problem is that the level of absorption of vocational school graduates is low, the curriculum is not yet in line with the industrial world, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, teachers are less competent, there is monotonous learning in the classroom, and the problem of connectivity between vocational schools and the industrial world (Widiatna, 2019). The complex problems in vocational school management require school principals to have strong managerial skills to meet these demanding needs.

Managerial skills for each level of the organization include conceptual, social, and operational skills with different compositions according to manager level (Usman, 2009). Mintzberg (2009) states that there are 10 managerial roles. Managers can play roles from the interpersonal aspect (figurehead, leader, liaison), informational aspect (monitor, disseminator, spokesperson), and decisional aspect (entrepreneur, disturbance handler, resource allocator, negotiator).

The principal's interpersonal role is as a symbol, leader, and liaison. The principal as a symbol can be seen from the principal representing his school in attending official and unofficial ceremonies in schools and government/private sectors, receiving guests, delivering speeches, attending wedding invitations for educators and educational staff, and looking around. The principal as a leader can be seen as a leader who leads the school to utilize school resources optimally. Leaders can develop a vision and implement the school's vision. As a liaison, the principal must communicate with internal and external contacts. As manager of school relations with the community, the principal must create an effective network on behalf of the school organization (Mace, 2013).

The informational role, namely receiving and conveying information, is the most essential aspect for every school principal. The principal's role as a monitor is constantly seeking information inside and outside the school. The role of the school principal as a disseminator is to distribute vital information to educators and education staff, parents of students, school committee members, school boards, government officials, and the community. The principal's role as a spokesperson is like a diplomat. As a diplomat, the principal must speak diplomatically, fascinate his audience, and be ready to carry out what the principal speaks (Altamont et al., 2017).

The role of the school principal from the decisional aspect is that the principal is an entrepreneur. School principals must be creative and innovative in developing the school by creating educational products/services to market the school so that the school can be a source of entrepreneurial learning for students and as a source of school funding. The role of the school principal as a disturbance is the principal's ability to handle disturbances that impact the school. The principal's role is as a manager of change and development and creator of school culture and climate (Al-Safran et al., 2014).

There are eight functions of a school principal as a manager, namely 1) working with and through other people; 2) with limited time and resources, able to face various problems; 3) being responsible and able to be held accountable; 4) think realistically and conceptually; 5) as an intermediary; 6) is a politician; 7) is a diplomat; and 8) making difficult decisions (Kristiawan et al., 2017).

In times of crisis, people look to their leaders and hope they will minimize the impact of the crisis. Leaders in such situations must understand and overcome the crisis while maintaining a sense of normality (Hugs & Molaodi, 2021). Meanwhile, the challenges faced by school leaders during the COVID-19 pandemic have been discussed extensively in many research articles. Intelligent school leaders during COVID-19 showed leadership in supporting schools during the education crisis (Farrell, 2021).

In this moment of the COVID-19 pandemic, educational leaders face increasing pressure to take a transformative leadership stance committed to racial justice, where curriculum, pedagogy, policies, norms, and mindsets are critically assessed and transformed into a new normative state of anti-racism. Flux leadership is a framework for fair, responsive, and agile leadership in continuous, complex, and multifaceted change. Flux leadership creates the conditions for flux pedagogy by taking a leadership stance focused on inquiry and justice (Ravitch, 2020).

The main dimensions of flux leadership, according to Ravitch (2020), consist of 1) Radical growth mindset; 2) Distributed wisdom approach; 3) Leading from an inquiry stance; 4) Trauma-informed leadership; 5) Feelings of love and care (radical compassion and radical self-care); 6) Responsive and humanizing leadership; 7) Critical pedagogy leader (critical pedagogy leader); 8) Racial literacy; 9) Brave leadership (brave space leadership); 10) Emotional imagination and inner-resource cultivation.

The core theory of flux leadership is familiar and is an existing framework for theory, research, policy, and practice that supports school and educational equity. Critical integration and application constitute a responsive, equity-centered pedagogical framework practical when leading through global, national, state, and local crises. A flux leadership mindset helps leaders to identify and examine deficit-based social constructs of race that shape curriculum, teaching, and schooling (Pak & Ravitch, 2021).]

Figure 1: Flux Leadership Factors Framework

METHOD

The research was carried out using a quantitative approach using survey methods. The research was conducted in June - August 2022. The research location was at vocational schools in the Special Region of Yogyakarta, with a population of all schools and/or deputy principals of vocational schools. The sampling technique used purposive sampling, namely school principals and/or deputy principals of vocational schools in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The data collection technique uses a questionnaire.

The questionnaire as a research instrument was prepared based on aspects of Flux Leadership as the main dimensions adopted from Ravitch (2020):

- 1) Radical growth mindset
- 2) Distributed wisdom approach
- 3) Leading from an inquiry stance

- 4) trauma-informed leadership
- 5) Radical compassion and radical self-care
- 6) Responsive and humanizing leadership
- 7) Leader critical pedagogy
- 8) Racial literacy
- 9) Brave space leadership
- 10) Emotional imagination and inner-resource cultivation

Data obtained from the field is then analyzed using statistical analysis. The data analysis results will provide an overview in answering the research objectives. The data analysis technique used in this research is the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) analysis technique using SmartPLS software.

RESULTS

This research involved 60 school principals and deputy principals of vocational schools in the Special Region of Yogyakarta with characteristics as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Characteristics (N=60)

Variable	Characteristics	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	28	46,67
	Woman	32	53,33
Age	26 – 35 years old	7	11,67
	36 – 45 years old	34	56,67
	46 – 55 years old	19	31,67
Department	Headmaster	28	46,67
	vice principal	32	53,33
Length of Service	13 years old	23	38,33
	4 - 5 years old	29	48,33
	6 - 10 years old	8	13,33

Researchers have prepared an instrument in the form of a questionnaire which was distributed to several vocational schools with school principals and deputy principals as respondents. Then the instrument that has been prepared is tested for convergent and discriminant validity to determine whether the initial model that has been prepared meets the validity requirements.

Figure 4: Initial Model CFA Analysis Results

a. Convergent Validity

This test can see that the loading factor value >0.50 is said to be valid. Based on the results of data processing, it shows that there are 3 items that do not meet the requirements, namely the loading factor value < 0.05 and were removed from the research instrument.

Table 2: Convergent Validity

	Brave Space	Compassion Self-care	Critical Pedagogy	Distributed Wisdom	Emotional Imagination	Grow Mindset	Inquiry Stance	Racial Literacy	Responsive Humanizing	Trauma Informed
BS1	0.888									
BS2	0.854									
BS3	0.851									
CP1			0.912							
CP2			0.783							
CP3			0.924							
CP4			0.902							
CS1		0.822								
CS2		0.786								
CS3		0.799								
DW1				0.483						
DW2				0.680						
DW3				0.756						
DW4				0.393						
DW5				0.381						
EI1					0.919					
EI2					0.518					
EI3					0.842					
EI4					0.690					
GM1						0.796				
GM2						0.846				
GM3						0.699				
IS1							0.604			
IS2							0.849			
IS3							0.908			
IS4							0.902			
RH1									0.515	
RH2									0.937	
RH3									0.900	
RL1								0.865		
RL2								0.911		
RL3								0.825		
RL4								0.617		
TI1										0.886
TI2										0.823
TI3										0.828
TI4										0.676

b. Discriminant Validity

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

	Brave Space	Compassion Selfcare	Critical Pedagogy	Distributed Wisdom	Emotional Imagination	Grow Mindset	Inquiry Stance	Racial Literacy	Responsive Humanizing	Trauma Informed
BS1	0.888	0.407	0.484	0.341	0.361	0.335	0.249	0.552	0.466	0.258
BS2	0.854	0.232	0.306	0.172	0.446	0.187	0.093	0.338	0.258	0.085
BS3	0.851	0.226	0.410	0.125	0.282	0.220	0.038	0.421	0.399	0.015
CP1	0.482	0.217	0.912	0.281	0.251	0.318	0.168	0.850	0.841	0.265
CP2	0.361	0.397	0.783	0.327	0.294	0.150	0.360	0.601	0.586	0.479
CP3	0.381	0.317	0.924	0.180	0.296	0.217	0.118	0.754	0.739	0.283
CP4	0.444	0.300	0.902	0.324	0.262	0.379	0.118	0.687	0.816	0.327
CS1	0.204	0.822	0.405	0.281	0.163	0.139	0.441	0.311	0.328	0.636
CS2	0.293	0.786	0.159	0.244	0.137	0.396	0.533	0.214	0.095	0.458
CS3	0.361	0.799	0.245	0.324	0.259	0.153	0.427	0.168	0.227	0.498
DW1	0.133	0.052	0.245	0.483	0.015	0.430	0.268	0.168	0.284	0.139
DW2	0.091	0.171	0.117	0.680	0.205	0.288	0.024	0.038	0.283	0.214
DW3	0.291	0.252	0.319	0.756	0.229	0.278	0.123	0.173	0.402	0.365
DW4	0.127	0.101	0.088	0.393	0.097	0.244	0.204	0.137	0.133	0.233
DW5	0.004	0.425	-0.004	0.381	-0.067	0.065	0.474	0.031	0.077	0.450
EI1	0.354	0.192	0.238	0.142	0.919	-0.142	-0.068	0.107	0.174	0.188
EI2	0.196	0.208	0.123	0.105	0.518	0.065	0.004	0.180	0.158	0.086
EI3	0.307	0.269	0.309	0.143	0.842	0.012	-0.001	0.144	0.248	0.203
EI4	0.391	0.014	0.240	0.199	0.690	0.031	-0.015	0.152	0.119	0.128
GM1	0.292	0.218	0.316	0.391	0.024	0.796	0.326	0.297	0.395	0.229
GM2	0.156	0.286	0.206	0.329	-0.074	0.846	0.321	0.278	0.311	0.072
GM3	0.242	0.137	0.171	0.404	0.007	0.699	0.134	0.333	0.393	-0.028
IS1	0.165	0.412	0.098	0.168	0.003	0.280	0.604	0.192	0.048	0.421
IS2	0.088	0.572	0.181	0.312	-0.055	0.252	0.849	0.226	0.102	0.636
IS3	0.169	0.479	0.265	0.373	-0.013	0.270	0.908	0.275	0.156	0.505
IS4	0.128	0.436	0.140	0.316	-0.018	0.343	0.902	0.224	0.085	0.423
RH1	0.397	0.208	0.304	0.198	0.282	0.280	0.023	0.411	0.515	0.084
RH2	0.395	0.175	0.826	0.393	0.112	0.462	0.172	0.779	0.937	0.245
RH3	0.333	0.306	0.809	0.477	0.236	0.376	0.076	0.620	0.900	0.309
RL1	0.352	0.223	0.714	0.198	0.216	0.348	0.123	0.865	0.765	0.193
RL2	0.395	0.208	0.830	0.197	0.204	0.313	0.246	0.911	0.747	0.231
RL3	0.375	0.257	0.646	0.098	-0.010	0.269	0.282	0.825	0.554	0.091
RL4	0.622	0.284	0.434	0.185	0.192	0.322	0.282	0.617	0.371	0.082
TI1	0.213	0.566	0.342	0.453	0.227	0.103	0.559	0.180	0.266	0.886
TI2	0.095	0.530	0.342	0.394	0.140	0.075	0.364	0.116	0.228	0.823
TI3	0.091	0.637	0.277	0.468	0.157	0.195	0.586	0.216	0.272	0.828
TI4	0.098	0.395	0.274	0.270	0.136	0.033	0.422	0.084	0.116	0.676

The results of the cross loading table above show that there are 3 variable items that have a value of <0.50 or the correlation to the variable is lower than the correlation to other variables, therefore the three items are discriminantly invalid and must be removed from the research

instrument. Meanwhile, the other items have the highest correlation in the latent variable, therefore the discriminant items are valid and suitable for analysis at the next research stage.

a. Reliability and AVE

Table 7: Reliability and AVE of the Revised Model

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Brave_Space	0.835	0.873	0.899	0.748
Compassion_Selfcare	0.725	0.733	0.844	0.643
Critical_Pedagogy	0.903	0.905	0.933	0.778
Distributed_Wisdom	0.747	0.897	0.881	0.788
Emotional_Imagination	0.733	0.775	0.838	0.575
Grow_Mindset	0.684	0.698	0.825	0.613
Inquiry_Stance	0.835	0.861	0.893	0.681
Racial_Literacy	0.821	0.844	0.884	0.661
Responsive_Humanizing	0.706	0.801	0.841	0.651
Trauma_Informed	0.819	0.840	0.881	0.651

Based on the reliability results above, it is known that all variables have a Composite reliability value of > 0.60, this shows that the variables have good reliability. All variables also have an AVE value > 0.50, this shows that these variables have good convergent validity.

b. R-Square

Table 8: R-Square Value

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Brave Space	0.405	0.395
Compassion Selfcare	0.403	0.393
Critical Pedagogy	0.753	0.749
Distributed Wisdom	0.184	0.170
Emotional Imagination	0.153	0.138
Grow Mindset	0.261	0.248
Inquiry Stance	0.260	0.247
Racial Literacy	0.657	0.651
Responsive Humanizing	0.670	0.664
Trauma Informed	0.358	0.347

The CFA test results also show the R Squared correlation value which shows the large contribution of each factor to the formation of the Flux Leadership construct.

DISCUSSION

Table 4: Leadership Flux Level of Vocational School Principals

Factors	Item	Principal Statement of Flux Leadership	Mean	Std Dev
radical growth mindset	GM1	I have a certain amount of intelligence that I can't do much to change	3.37	0.88
	GM2	My intelligence is something about me that cannot be changed.	3.23	0.83
	GM3	I can learn new things, but I can't change my basic intelligence	3.00	1.00
distributed wisdom approach	DW1	I have overcome many painful events in my life	3.50	0.72
	DW2	It is easy for me to adjust my emotions to the situation at hand	3.87	0.34
	DW3	Remembering my previous days helps me gain insight into important things in life	4.13	0.63
	DW4	I try to find the funny side when facing big life transitions	3.30	0.64
	DW5	I like being around people whose views are very different from my own	3.37	0.48
leading from an inquiry stance	IS1	When I started as principal at my new school, I felt I knew best what action steps and type of leadership the school needed before I talked to teachers, students, and community members.	4.17	0.59
	IS2	At my school, education staff and teachers have a high level of trust in each other	3.37	0.88
	IS3	As a principal, I see teachers as true partners in fostering the changes necessary for school progress	3.87	1.41
	IS4	As a principal, I respect teachers' differing opinions about the school's mission and operations	3.50	1.16
trauma-informed leadership	TI1	I recognize the far-reaching impact of Covid-19 trauma and understand the path to recovery	4.03	0.72
	TI2	I recognize the signs and symptoms of Covid-19 trauma in educators and teachers, and other people involved in schools	3.93	0.78
	TI3	I integrate knowledge about Covid-19 trauma into school policies, procedures and practices	3.77	0.43
	TI4	I try to help education staff and teachers actively fight re-traumatization	3.90	0.61
radical compassion and radical self-care	CS1	Concern myself to choose strategies that will benefit the school	4.00	0.69
	CS2	My self-care made it radically a top priority	4.03	0.69
	CS3	I plan a plan by reflecting on self-care	3.63	0.49
responsive and humanizing leadership	RH1	I self-reflect on ways to influence other people	3.97	1.03
	RH2	I treat people as important people	4.03	0.72
	RH3	I apply humanizing leadership	3.90	0.61
leader critical pedagogy	CP1	I practice emotional healing and put students	4.30	0.64

		first		
	CP2	I create value for society	3.90	0.30
	CP3	I empower and help students grow and succeed	4.40	0.67
	CP4	I demonstrate conceptual skills	3.93	0.78
racial literacy	RL1	I am against undemocratic practices	3.77	0.86
	RL2	I appreciate diverse and unfamiliar experiences	4.00	0.00
	RL3	I recognize race/ethnicity as a structural problem rather than an individual problem	3.50	0.72
	RL4	I facilitate problem solving in the community	3.77	0.43
brave space leadership	BS1	I am making more of a conscious effort to address vulnerabilities on-site at school	4.03	0.49
	BS2	As a leader I must be confident in stepping out of my comfort zone	3.93	0.74
	BS3	Critical thinking as a valuable attribute in my leadership	4.03	0.49
emotional imagination and inner-resource cultivation	EI1	I express what I know and feel about school policies	4.03	0.49
	EI2	I feel the tension as a school leader	2.90	0.94
	EI3	I have an understanding of leadership and myself as a school leader	3.90	0.61
	EI4	I know the contribution patterns of stakeholders in the school community	3.80	0.41

Radical growth mindset

Self-care, healing, mindfulness, and spiritual dimensions are now part of the struggle for radical social justice. School principals, staff, students, parents, and communities are experiencing pandemic fatigue. Educational leaders also experience burnout at the start of a new school year without additional support. This moment of the COVID-19 pandemic is special for leaders who must intentionally take care of themselves for many reasons, including so that they have the energy needed to support students, teachers, families, and each other. To do this, leaders must understand social identities regarding their proximity to structural forces and resources.

The ability to conceptualize and articulate how systems of domination and marginalization emerge daily at the individual, group, and community levels is critical for leaders. A radical growth mindset is an internal imperative to understand reality in order to alleviate the distress, pain, and suffering of others. Radical compassion stems from a critique of schools as places that create, exacerbate, deny, and ignore students' distress and struggles, but rather as places that help students achieve optimal development.

Distributed wisdom approach

This shift in power dynamics is when leaders centralize wisdom to push everyone into a hierarchy of knowledge, which is a distributed wisdom approach. At a time when most students, teachers, families, and communities feel powerless, leaders creating conditions where they can feel like sharing feelings, perspectives, experiences, ideas, and concerns without fear is critical to learning inside and outside of school. (Eren & Ravitch, 2021).

Leading through a distributed wisdom approach is transformative for principals and school organizations. Principals need to position themselves as learners to understand how this shapes professional leadership practice increasingly critically. Inquiry as an attitude, the basis of the shifting pedagogical mindset, requires leaders to adopt a reflective learning stance about self, context, and professional practice.

Leading from an inquiry stance

Leading from an inquiry stance is described as a habit of critical thinking and a dynamic way of understanding educational practices that can lead to professional careers and educational settings. This attitude encourages leaders to see and appreciate the collective intellectual capacity of the practitioners they work with.

Principals view their schools and communities as sites of knowledge generation occurring within specific historical, cultural, and political contexts (Lytle et al., 2018). Leading from an inquiry stance offers a leadership theory and approach that effectively builds on maturing research into school leadership. Leading from the inquiry stance is the theory conceptualized by Lytle et al. (2018), who carefully consider the school context to encourage the adaptive work needed to meet the school's challenge of achieving positive student achievement.

Trauma-informed leadership

We need to develop new leadership competencies throughout the leadership journey to meet changing workplace expectations. Now, entering a post-COVID-19 environment, an essential competency for school principals is how to use a trauma-informed approach in their leadership. The experience of Covid-19 has caused trauma for many stakeholders in schools. Leaders are concerned about their staff's trauma but are unsure how to respond. Identifying COVID-19 as a trauma and using trauma-informed strategies in leadership is essential.

Understanding COVID-19 as a trauma and a victim of trauma helps explain anger, negativity, and excessive emotional reactions to situations in the school environment. Trauma-informed leadership acknowledges and respects the emotional scars others have. This can help principals empathize with teachers, employees, and students with a leader's emotions.

Radical compassion and radical self-care

Flux leadership supports the principal's self-care as a leader. The leadership dimensions of flux, while not new, are exponentially more salient today as they each demonstrate how identity shapes the experience of this multifaceted crisis and how critical approaches can help organize confusion by offering a pathway to radically new mindsets for educational leadership and pedagogical practice (Ravitch, 2020).

Responsive and humanizing leadership

Petriglieri and Petriglieri (2015) argue that dehumanizing leadership exists in organizational cultures that devalue learning. There is widespread agreement that schools prepare leaders whose actions and values reflect amoral ideologies, a lack of concern for society, a positive attitude toward greed, and gender bias.

Leader critical pedagogy

Critical pedagogy positions students as knowing agents who investigate, question, and critique social and educational norms concerning their own experiences. Students are seen as passive recipients of the teacher's knowledge transmission; it can also position teachers as transformative intellectuals in a system that often renders them unprofessional. Critical pedagogy positions students as critical citizens with the will and skills to act as change agents. Cultivating students' critical awareness is part of building education as a practice of freedom of thought. It helps students work together to create conditions where they can cultivate a sense of agency regarding what many people today experience as helplessness, confusion, and hopelessness.

Racial literacy

We use a racial literacy framework to highlight the importance of recognizing, responding to, and confronting everyday racism, especially in the classroom. We conceptualize race as a social and historical concept shaped and reformed by individuals and groups throughout society. As a socially constructed concept, race is relational and assigns levels of privilege and power to people in particular settings (Vetter & Hungerford-Watercress, 2014).

Brave space leadership

Brave spaces are spaces where people can be authentic, honest, and vulnerable in their experiences so that we can push forward and collaborate effectively. Through Brave Space, we can realize shared leadership and shared strength. People are capable of being their authentic selves (Beschoner,

Ferrero, B. (2021). Schools need participative leaders, not just one person we see. Everyone has a valuable story and perspective; we must create spaces to be brave enough to show that. Models' brave **leadership** appears to aid decision-making, and courage can be enhanced, at least from a subjective perspective (McLaughlin, 2013).

Emotional imagination and inner-resource cultivation

School principals, as leaders, need to be aware of what affects them emotionally to be effective, ethical, and accountable. Principals need to understand emotional imagination and inner-resource cultivation to navigate stress related to other people's identities effectively. Understanding how to navigate times of intense emotion for oneself and as an expected part of organizational life is a vital leadership skill. This is even more urgent now as people return to school exhausted and with high emotions, considering everything happening post-pandemic (Judson, 2021). Leaders need to know that there are several common triggers, which include: 1) feeling self-conscious, 2) feeling ignored, 3) feeling controlled, 4) feeling used, 5) feeling vulnerable, 6) relationship experiences, 7) boundary concerns, 8) feeling uncomfortable with what happened, 9) afraid of what might happen (Richo, 2019).

CONCLUSION

COVID-19 has increased the need to strengthen our knowledge of how to build practical leadership in organizational sustainability. School principals in crisis need high-level leadership to direct teachers, employees, and students to achieve organizational goals. However, new policies for post-COVID-19, such as social distancing, working, and learning from home, have intervened in the trust and relationships between school principals, teachers, employees, and students. The remote work environment has impacted organizational leadership. As a result, principals must find ways to solve problems, such as reducing online work hours and asking employees to return to traditional workplaces to make teachers and employees feel that they are valuable to the organization.

This study can help school principals improve their organizational sustainability leadership skills. School principals need to understand what factors influence leadership in the organization to adapt to the uncertainty of the post-Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, managers can develop flux leadership skills, especially after COVID-19.

These results can help school principals understand what factors positively or negatively impact leadership in the organization to improve their leadership skills, even post-COVID-19. The managerial implication is that leaders need good communication skills to share correct information with empathy and optimism. Leaders must be wise and able to handle change in ethically uncertain situations.

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